

Visitors' Attitude towards the Service Marketing Mix and Frequency of Visits to Bangpu Recreation Centre, Thailand

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Abstract : This research paper was aimed to examine the relationship between visitors' attitude towards the service marketing mix and visitors' frequency of visit to Bangpu Recreation Centre. Based on a large and uncalculated population, the number of samples was calculated according to the formula to obtain a total of 385 samples. In collecting the samples, systematic random sampling was applied and by using of a Likert five-scale questionnaire for, a total of 21 days to collect the needed information. Mean, Standard Deviation, and Pearson's basic statistical correlations were utilized in analyzing the data. This study discovered a high level of visitors' attitude product and service of Bangpu Recreation Centre, price, place, promotional activities, people who provided service and physical evidence of the centre. The attitude towards process of service was discovered to be at a medium level. Additionally, the finding of an examination of a relationship between visitors' attitude towards service marketing mix and visitors' frequency of visit to Bangpu Recreation Centre presented that product and service, people, physical evidence and process of service provision showed a relationship with the visitors' frequency of visit to the centre per year.

Keywords : frequency of visit, visitor, service marketing mix, Bangpu Recreation Centre

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